

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2019-20 academic year for BPT

BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID

**COLLEGE OF
PHYSIOTHERAPY**
Value Added Course
**BASIC NURSING &
FIRST AID**

**FOR BPT (2019 BATCH)
UNDERGRADUATES**

**Learn Lifesaving Skills
From the Experts**

Course Duration: 40 hours

CONTACT
College of Physiotherapy, Ground floor, Srinivas
University City campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru
Phone: 0824-2429139
Email: deanphysiotherapy@srinivasuniversity.edu.in
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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Course period	From January 2020 till March 2020, during 2 nd semester (10 weeks)
Duration	40 hours (4 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 1 st year undergraduates (2019 batch)

Course Objectives:

- Understand the new responsibilities of an Occupational First Aider.
- To be familiar with health & safety legislation on first aid in the workplace (e.g. Contents of First Aid Box)

Course Outline:

Week	Lectures	Assignments	Hour ¹
Module 1 «Introduction to nursing and nursing positions»			
1-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is nursing? Nursing principles. Inter personnel relationships. Basic turns: Bandaging extremities: Triangular Bandages and their application. • Nursing position: Environment safety: Bed making, prone, lateral, dorsal, dorsal recumbent, Fowler's positions, comfort measures, Aids and rest and sleep. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Home assignments ✓ Lab: Practice of nursing positions 	8
Module 2 «Bedside management and methods of Nourishment»			
3-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bed side Management: Giving and taking Bed pan, Urinal: Observation of stools, Urine. Observation of Sputum, Understand use and care of care of catheters, enema giving • Lifting and transporting patients: Lifting patient up in the bed, transferring from bed to wheel chair, transferring from bed to stretcher • Methods of giving Nourishment: Feeding, tube feeding, Tube feeding, drips, transfusion. • Observation of surgical procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Assignments ✓ Lab: Practice sessions 	12
Module 3 «First Aid»			

6-7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of first aid in physiotherapy • Instrumentation used in First Aid (First Aid kit) • Examination of Vital signs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Home Assignments ✓ Lab: Demonstrations and practice 	8
Module 4 «First Aid procedures»			
8-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Aid in cardiac arrest and in Respiratory failure • First Aid in Burns, Electric shock, Hypovolemic shock and Drowning • First Aid in Spinal cord injuries; Poisoning; RTA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Demonstrations and case studies 	12

¹ Hours designed for Classroom sessions, video tutorials, Home Assignments, Activities etc.

Attendance Policy

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

Book References:

1. I Clement. Text book on First Aid & Emergency Nursing. Jaypee Brothers.
2. N.N Yalayaswamy. First Aid & Emergency Nursing, CBS publishers.
3. Indian First Aid manual. 7th ed. St. John. Ambulance Association, 2017.
4. Glassey N. Physiotherapy for burns & Reconstruction. Wiley, 2004.
5. Harris N. First Aid and Emergency care, AITBS Publishers.
6. Golwalla A. F. Golwalla S. K. A handbook of emergencies, Jaypee Brothers.

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

ABDUL AMEEN RASHID (5SU19PT001)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

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Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

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ABHAYASREE M (5SU19PT002)

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Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

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ADITHYA M (5SU19PT003)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

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College of Physiotherapy
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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

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AHAMMED NASEEH V B (5SU19PT004)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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AISHWARYA BIJUSH (5SU19PT005)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

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Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
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Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
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Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
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ALBIN JACOB VARUGHESE (5SU19PT006)

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Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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ANAMIKA K (5SU19PT007)

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College of Physiotherapy
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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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ANJANA MANOJ (5SU19PT008)

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College of Physiotherapy
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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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ANJANA MOHAN (5SU19PT009)

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Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
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ANJIMA K V (5SU19PT010)

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
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Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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ATHIRA P KRISHNA (5SU19PT011)

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College of Physiotherapy
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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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AYESHA SAFEERA (5SU19PT012)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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AYSHA FARHA (5SU19PT013)

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Srinivas University

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Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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BAGHELE AISHWARYA RAJESH (5SU19PT014)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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BENECIA ANITA CARDOZO (5SU19PT015)

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College of Physiotherapy
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Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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BHAVYASHREE C VAIDYA (5SU19PT016)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CHANNAMMA R NELAGUDDA (5SU19PT017)

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CHARAN JITENDRA VAIDYA (5SU19PT018)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Assistant Professor
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CHAUHAN KAVITA BABURAM (5SU19PT019)

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Srinivas University

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Assistant Professor
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DANY ELDHOSE (5SU19PT020)

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Srinivas University

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DEEPTHI K J (5SU19PT021)

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Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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DI – ANN VERA VAZ (5SU19PT022)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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DIAS RICHA CHRISTINE (5SU19PT023)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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FARSANA T (5SU19PT024)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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FATHIMA (5SU19PT025)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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FATHIMA ARSANA (5SU19PT026)

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Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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FATHIMABI (5SU19PT027)

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Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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presented to

FINU ANTONY (5SU19PT028)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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GIFIN M PAUL (5SU19PT029)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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GOKUL A P (5SU19PT030)

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presented to

GREESHMA M EDWIN (5SU19PT031)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
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Srinivas University

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Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
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presented to

HARSHITHA G S (5SU19PT032)

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Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
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HAZEBA FATHIMA (5SU19PT033)

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HEMANTH A V (5SU19PT034)

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HRUTHIKA M (5SU19PT035)

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IFTHISHAM (5SU19PT036)

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JANE CARYN LOBO (5SU19PT037)

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JILSHA P Y (5SU19PT038)

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Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

JOYCE MARIAM JOSY (5SU19PT040)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

KARUNA VISHRAM PARAB (5SU19PT041)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

KRISHNAPRIYA BIJU (5SU19PT042)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

LUGELLE MARIA DE GRACA FERNANDES (5SU19PT043)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

MARIYAMMA (5SU19PT044)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

MEHTAB JUBAPU SHUAIB (5SU19PT045)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

MOHAMMED TAHA (5SU19PT046)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

MUHAMMED RASIL P M (5SU19PT047)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

MUHAMMED SAFVAN P (5SU19PT048)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

MUHAMMED SINAN K (5SU19PT049)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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presented to

MUHAMMED SHANID P (5SU19PT050)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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MUHSIN K.P (5SU19PT051)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

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Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

NEELINA K (5SU19PT052)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

NIRMAL JAIN (5SU19PT053)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

PEARL ASTIDA D'SA (5SU19PT054)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

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Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

PRIYANTH A (5SU19PT055)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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PUSHPA N NAYAK (5SU19PT056)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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presented to

RAGHAVENDRA A N (5SU19PT057)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

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Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

RAHUL E S (5SU19PT058)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

RATHIKA RAVINDRA NAYAK (5SU19PT059)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

RAVI R H (5SU19PT060)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

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Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

REMYA RAVEENDRAN (5SU19PT061)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

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RIFNA KOUSAR (5SU19PT062)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

RINSHIDA N P (5SU19PT063)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SAIDH ALI HAMZA (5SU19PT064)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SANDRA K R (5SU19PT065)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SANGAR SHIVANI NAVIN (5SU19PT066)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SANGEETH SANTHOSH (5SU19PT067)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SAYED FARZANA PARVEEN (5SU19PT068)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SEBINNABI TORGAL (5SU19PT069)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SHAHISTHA BANU (5SU19PT070)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SHAIKH SUMERA MEHEK NASEEM IRFAN (5SU19PT071)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

SHAJAHAN (5SU19PT072)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

SHIFANA M E (5SU19PT073)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SHRAMIKA (5SU19PT074)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Annayya Kulal'.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

SHRIRAKSHA R ANGADI (5SU19PT075)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

STACY SANTAN FERNANDES (5SU19PT076)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

SWETHA P S (5SU19PT077)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

SYED MOHAMMED S J (5SU19PT078)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dr. S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
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College of Physiotherapy
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Assistant Professor
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Srinivas University

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TIDKE ANIKET NIRAJ (5SU19PT079)

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College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

presented to

VARSHINI B (5SU19PT080)

for attending and completing the course on "BASIC NURSING AND FIRST AID"
held from January 2020 till March 2020

Total Hours- 40

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

Dr. S. RAJASEKAR
Professor and Dean
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

Handwritten signature of Dr. Annayya Kulal in blue ink.

Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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presented to

YASSER K V (5SU19PT081)

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College of Physiotherapy
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Dr. ANNAYYA KULAL
Chief Medical officer and
Assistant Professor
College of Physiotherapy
Srinivas University

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

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ZAHWA MUNEER (5SU19PT082)

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Srinivas University

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